

A day without the press

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A scenario without media seems impossible, however, there are reasons to think that the free press is weak, and its disappearance is approaching, unless some conditions are changed.

The growth of disinformation, the modification of the business model, labour precariousness, gender inequality, threats, and attacks against journalists resulting in exile, among other circumstances, imply less quality news, a weak public opinion and the deterioration of democracy.

The media are fundamental for life in society, which is why international organizations and intergovernmental bodies are debating the sustainability of newspapers, news Websites, radio stations and other spaces to guarantee a deontological treatment of information, the participation of citizens and offer audiences critical elements for decision-making.

But, despite the risks described above, the community shows little sensitivity to the potential loss of news, perhaps collective laboratories should be created where people look at what commerce, security and their own coexistence would be like without free media. This intention emerged as a proposal of expanded narratives that a group of communication professors from Loja rehearse in the workshop #NarrarelFuturo: "Festival de cine & nuevos medios" to, in addition to educate, explore the possibilities, potentialities, and limitations of the models of content circulation and support for the civic role of the press.

The country of tomorrow is thought and modeled in the classroom. Showing what a day without newspapers will be like is an experiment to move people and their leaders to seek changes that guarantee ample information, tolerance and less conflict.